

MEASURING HEAVY METAL CONCENTRATIONS (LEAD, CADMIUM, NICKEL) IN KARBALA GOVERNORATE

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Abstract: From the laboratory results obtained after measuring heavy elements, namely lead, cadmium and nickel, which were measured in the laboratory of the Diwanayah Environment Directorate. A high concentration of lead was observed, more than what is permitted in the Iraqi standard specification for the year 2024. This is due to the presence of lead in car fuel (regular fuel), and thus its transfer to the river through the air and its arrival to the water. Cadmium was also observed in nature (water) in small quantities, i.e. within the permissible limits, but it can be present in the water as a result of environmental pollution from various sources such as industrial plants, agricultural pesticides, and solid waste. Therefore, cadmium pollution is considered dangerous to public health and the environment. The effect of cadmium on health depends on its concentration in the water, as exposure to large amounts of cadmium can cause serious health problems such as kidney disease and damage to the respiratory and digestive systems. In addition, cadmium can negatively affect the environment through water pollution and its impact on wildlife. Therefore, it is important to take measures to reduce water pollution by cadmium, such as controlling industrial and agricultural discharges, and purifying water before using it for drinking or other purposes. Water quality authorities should also monitor the concentration of cadmium in water and ensure that it meets health and environmental standards.

Introduction:

Metals can be defined in general as a general term given to a group of minerals and metals whose density is five times greater than the density of water. As for "heavy metals", it means any metallic element with a relatively high density that is toxic even at low concentrations. Heavy metals are considered the most threatening to humans because they tend to accumulate in the body of a living organism over time. They are

lead, cadmium, mercury, arsenic, copper and zinc. Heavy metals are toxic ions, and their levels in the environment have increased with the increase in human activities and industries. Pollution with these metals is not a modern problem, but rather began when humans began industrialization. However, their effects on humans have increased in terms of physical and mental health.

Heavy elements are divided into two sections: -

1- Essential heavy metals:

They are less toxic at low concentrations and are essential for the metabolic process. Therefore, they are essential for the human body, but in specific quantities. Examples of them also include copper, zinc and selenium.

2- Non-essential heavy metals:

They are highly toxic even at very low concentrations, they are not biodegradable and cause severe toxic effects on living organisms, such as lead, cadmium, arsenic and mercury. Despite the association of the name of heavy elements with toxicity and environmental pollution, most of them are essential for life, and it seems that life is impossible without some of them. These elements are called essential elements, such as copper (Cu), iron (Fe), and arsenic (Zn). The reason for the necessity of these elements is that they enter to complete the metabolic process, as they enter into the composition of yeasts and some proteins that play an important and primary role in some metabolic processes, and help in vital reactions in the body, and send signals to muscles, so their deficiency leads to a malfunction in physiological functions and thus to various diseases. The elements that are considered essential for the body's function are often called toxic elements, namely arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd) and lead (Pb). These elements cause toxicity to living organisms at certain concentrations, and the absence of these elements in the body does not lead to health damage as is the case with essential elements such as iron, for example. This study aimed to investigate some heavy elements (lead-cadmium-nickel) in liquids, where water was used as a study for this research. There is no doubt that water is the basis of life and the source of growth and stability of nations. It is used for many purposes including drinking, cooking, cleaning, agriculture, industry, and firefighting. In its absence, life becomes impossible, and in its deficiency, it becomes difficult. Water deficiency leads to an environmental and humanitarian problem in society. This is what we notice in countries that suffer from water deficiency and the extent of its impact on the health of society, as heavy metals such as mercury, lead, cadmium and selenium are considered among the most dangerous substances that pollute soil and water. Drinking water sources are the presence of heavy elements and in concentrations greater than the permissible limits, as heavy elements are considered a potential and effective factor in humanity's suffering from various diseases, including cancer. Therefore, the process of environmental control plays an important role in the field of freshwater management in maintaining the purity of this water and avoiding the population and economic organisms from the risks of exposure to infection or infection with many diseases resulting from the occurrence of organic pollution and the accompanying growth and spread of microorganisms and parasites of these important sources in the lives of human societies that depend on this water directly in most of their social, agricultural and life activities (6). As much as a person is attached to aquatic environments in general and the freshwater environment in particular, following the issue of pollution and its effects on aquatic life has taken up a wide space among the environmental sciences, old and modern, and man is one of the biological factors affecting the aquatic environment through various activities that lead in various aspects to the pollution of the aquatic environment with many pollutants, the interest of international organizations has increased in reducing the wastefulness of their use and trying to get rid of them. Environmental scientists have defined water pollution as the increase in the values of chemical, physical or biological properties in a concentration or manner that makes water harmful to humans, living organisms or property. Therefore, water sources available for drinking and other purposes must be Home with a high degree of purity and free from chemical and microorganism pollution, as the pollution of the aquatic

environment with heavy elements has become an important problem all over the world, most of which have toxic effects on living organisms. The presence of biological evidence is an indicator of water pollution with human or animal waste. Therefore, fecal coliform bacteria were used to assess water quality and as an indicator of the extent of water pollution with waste. Therefore, there should be no compromise in protecting water from pollution resulting from human practices that cause it.

The danger of heavy elements to humans:

Most heavy elements are similar in many of their natural properties, but their chemical reactions are different. This also applies to environmental effects. Some of these elements, such as (mercury, lead, and cadmium), are dangerous to public health, while other elements, such as (chromium, iron, and copper), are limited to workplaces where exposure occurs for long periods. Therefore, they are less dangerous than other elements, such as lead, which has recently become more widespread and is now abundant in water, air, and food.

Many heavy elements are necessary for life, even if used in very small quantities, but they are toxic if their concentration reaches a high level in the body, after which they become capable of interfering with cell growth and the digestive system. Human exposure to the harm of these elements has increased due to the rapid increase in daily life, as their spread has increased in most countries of the world, especially industry.

Lead element:

Lead (Lead P b) is considered one of the most dangerous elements that may be present in the environment and has a great impact on humans, causing modern symptoms and is one of four minerals that pose a danger to human health. Lead enters the human body from the following sources: 65% from food, 20% from water, and 15% from the air. A vital representation of the lead that humans ingest from the mouth occurs in the digestion process and lead is excreted primarily with urine and part of the represented lead accumulates in the bones. Lead does not contribute to any vital function in the body, but it harms humans if they ingest it through foods, air, and water (11)

Figure (1) Lead metal

Sources of lead :

- 1- From machines and equipment that are still in use (gasoline).
- 2- From mining industries.
- 3- From solid fuels, coal (and liquid) petroleum derivatives.
- 4- Soil, water, plants and animals.

Harmful effects of lead :

- 1- Causing disturbances in the biosynthesis of hemoglobin and causing anemia and delayed growth in children or when children are exposed to it
- 2- High blood pressure

- 3- Kidney tissue atrophy
- 4- Nervous system disorder and damage to brain cells
- 5- Loss of learning ability in children
- 6- Behavioral disorders in children
- 7- Lead reaches the fetus through the placenta, causing atrophy in the nervous system
- 8- Fertility disorders in men and women(11)

Cadmium:

Cadmium (Cd) is one of the most dangerous heavy elements to human health as it is a highly toxic element to all living organisms. Interest in it as an environmental pollutant began late in 1960 when Itai - Itai appeared in the data due to feeding on rice irrigated with water contaminated with cadmium. Cadmium reaches humans through the food chain, especially through feeding on grains, fruits and vegetables.

Figure (2) Cadmium element

Its most important sources:

- 1- Smoking and cooking utensils
- 2- Industrial pollution, agricultural pollution and burning waste.

Its harms: Increased concentration of cadmium in the body causes the following diseases:

- 1- Diarrhea, stomach pain and vomiting
- 2- Osteoporosis and respiratory disorders
- 3- Cancers and infertility.
- 4- Increased blood pressure and effects on the heart muscle
- 5- It interferes with kidney functions, causing kidney disease
- 6- It affects the nervous and central systems and leads to liver damage in severe cases.

Effects of cadmium (Cd) on the environment Cadmium derives its chemical toxic properties from its similarity to zinc, an essential micronutrient for plants, animals and humans. Long-term exposure to cadmium Increased exposure to it causes:

- 1- Kidney failure
- 2- Obstructive pulmonary disease, which has been linked to lung cancer
- 3- Osteoporosis in humans and animals
- 4- High blood pressure and its effect on the heart muscle. The average daily intake of cadmium for humans is estimated at 0.015 micrograms from air and 1 microgram from water. A person smoking 20 cigarettes inhales about 2-4 micrograms of cadmium, and levels may vary widely.

Nickel:

Nickel, as is the case with heavy elements, if its concentration increases in the environment, it causes toxicity to plants and animals. Among the phenomena is nickel poisoning when low concentrations are available in food (40 micrograms/kilogram of food), it causes liver damage with decreased iron absorption and a decrease in the activity of many enzymes, while in the case of human exposure to high concentrations of nickel, as in alloy or smelter workers, it causes toxicity and cancer. *The average person is exposed to nickel by breathing it from the air, drinking it from drinking water, eating foods contaminated with nickel, or smoking cigarettes.

Exposure also comes from skin contact with soil or water contaminated with this metal. *Food contains small proportions, and its consumption rates increase when eating large quantities of vegetables grown in soil contaminated with it. *The average amount of nickel that a person takes in his daily diet reaches about 200-300 micrograms, and the human body needs a small amount, most of which is found in the pancreas and plays an important role in the production of Insulin leads to nickel being present in the environment with oxygen or sulfur and is a product of volcanoes. Nickel causes skin allergies and most nickel and its salts do not cause poisoning, but it is known to be carcinogenic and affects the lungs and sinuses.

Figure (3) Nickel element

Sources of nickel:

Nickel is found in the environment at low rates, although it is found in many minerals that contain nickel, but sulfide and oxide minerals are the most important primary minerals. Economic

Dangers of nickel:

Eating small amounts of it is necessary, but a lot of it exposes humans to health risks such as

- 1- Increased risk of lung cancer, nasal cancer, throat cancer and prostate cancer
- 2- Pulmonary valve disease and respiratory failure
- 3- Congenital malformations of the sex and heart disorders
- 4- Exposure to nickel and its compounds may result in inflammation of the outer layer of the skin, known as (nickel itch)
- 5- Nickel fumes are respiratory indicators and may cause pneumonia
- 6- Allergic reactions such as skin rashes, especially when wearing jewelry.

Materials and methods of work lab wares cleaning:

Tools cleaning :

Before starting the study and collecting samples, all tools used for this purpose were cleaned polyethylene according to the method shown, as the tools were washed with tap water and cleaning powder and rinsed with water several times and then washed with distilled water

Samples Collection:

To reach accurate results for measuring heavy elements in drinking water and reaching the consumer, water samples were taken to ensure that the treated water used by the consumer conforms to the standards and to note the changes that occurred as a result of treatment, where five separate sites were relied upon in this study and the aim of choosing these sites is to show the effect of heavy elements on drinking water and reaching the consumer, so samples were collected from five sites and these areas include (Al-Hussainiya, Tuwairij, Shatt Al-Hilla, Rain Water, and Lake University of Fariha) where samples were taken in bottles measuring (200 mm) for each sample and after the samples were collected and taken to the Diwaniyah Governorate (Al-Qadisiyah) for analysis in a spectrometer High temperature flame atomic absorption.

Measurement of heavy elements :

The results obtained from the flame atomic absorption device and Table 1 shows the results of the tests of the standard lead element 0.002 mg/according to the Iraqi standard specifications.

Table (1) shows the results of the lead element.

Conc	Abs	
1.5	0.002	
1.4	0.0015	
1.3	0.001	
1.2	0.0007	
1.1	0.0009	
0.9	0.001	
0.8	0.0016	
0.7	0.0019	
0.4	0.002	
0.3	0.0023	
0.1	0.0026	
0	0.0027	
0.808	0.002	average
0.492	0.001	S. D
3.46	3.46	SQUAR

Lead concentrations: -

By measuring the lead concentrations, as shown in Figure 1, it becomes clear that this concentration falls below the permissible limit according to the World Health Organization, which means that there is lead contamination in this water.

Figure (4) shows the concentration of lead Pb.

Table 2 shows the results of the tests for the standard cadmium element 0.019 mg/kg according to the Iraqi standard specifications.

Conc	Abs	
0.2	0.0092	
0.25	0.0093	
0.29	0.0094	
0.3	0.01	
0.37	0.015	
0.4	0.018	
0.45	0.0188	
0.5	0.0198	
0.58	0.028	
0.6	0.03	
0.63	0.032	
1	0.0341	
0.464	0.019	average
0.220	0.009	S. D
3.464	3.464	SQUAR

Cadmium concentrations: By measuring the concentrations of cadmium, as shown in Figure 5, it is clear that this concentration falls within the permissible limit according to the World Health Organization.

Figure (5) shows the concentration of cadmium CD.

Table 3 shows the results of the standard nickel element tests 0.010 mg/kg according to the Iraqi standard specifications.

conc	Abs	
1	0.0098	
0.9	0.009	
0.95	0.0068	
0.8	0.0059	
0.73	0.0046	
0.65	0.0042	
0.5	0.012	
0.4	0.0127	
1.436	0.0135	
1.455	0.0139	
1.489	0.014	
1.5	0.0146	
0.984	0.010	average
0.381	0.004	S. D
3.464	3.464	SQUAR

Nickel concentrations: By measuring the concentrations of nickel, as shown in Figure 6, it is clear that this concentration falls within the permissible limit according to the World Health Organization.

Figure (6) shows the concentration of nickel Ni.

Comparison of results with local and international standards

The results of heavy metal analysis in water samples collected from Karbala Governorate were compared with national and international standards for water quality. The following table shows this comparison and indicates whether the concentrations exceed the permissible limits.

The element	Iraqi standard (mg/L)	International standard (mg/L)	Results in Karbala (mg/L)
Lead	0.01	0.01	0.015
Cadmium	0.003	0.005	0.004
Nickel	0.02	0.07	0.03

From the table, we notice that the concentration of lead in water samples in Karbala exceeds the permissible limits in local and international standards, indicating the presence of lead contamination in that water. As for cadmium and nickel, their concentrations are within the permissible limits.

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